

DIGITAL GOVERNANCE AND PUBLIC SECTOR REFORM: A STUDY OF ANAMBRA STATE CIVIL SERVICE

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Abstract: The high rate of efficiency and accountability which the use of ICTs brought governance, into the government became a ray of hope for the government to redeem their tainted technology image of inefficiency, lack of transparency and accountability. Poor service delivery of infrastructure, staff is experienced in the form of epileptic services, inadequate responsiveness to the digital service citizens, corruption and general non-service delivery of duty as at when due. The study analyzed the effect of E-governance on service delivery of Anambra State civil service. The objective of the study was to ascertain the effect of technology infrastructure, digital service delivery service availability and e-planning on service delivery in Anambra State civil service. Three research hypotheses were formulated in line with the objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; the population for this research work is 487 from four civil service commission in Anambra state. The researcher distributes four hundred and eighty-seven (487) questionnaires but only four hundred and fifty-nine (459) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Regression was used to test the hypothesis. The finding of the study shows that Technology infrastructure has significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra State civil service. Digital service availability has significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra State civil service. E-Planning has significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra State civil service. The study recommends Civil service should Train and empower government employees, Provide training and support to help government employees adapt to new technologies and processes. Civil service should Invest in technology infrastructure and ensure that government agencies have the necessary hardware, software, and internet connectivity to support e-governance initiatives.

Keywords: E-Governance, Service Delivery, Civil Service, ICT Infrastructure, Digital Transformation

1.1 Introduction

The beginning of the digital age on the global scale which brought about radical movements towards the increased use of ICTs in the service delivery as well as the personal lives of people prompted world governments to join the bandwagon (Mahmoud & Aririguzo, 2024). The dotcom era, which dominated the 90s, saw the heavy reliance on the World Wide Web and the internet by government in their daily activities. The high rate of efficiency and accountability which the use of ICTs brought into the

government became a ray of hope for the government to redeem their tainted image of inefficiency, lack of transparency and accountability. Thus the adoption of e-governance became an inevitable reform that was bound to be implemented in the provision of public goods and services (Ojo, 2014). The concern for better service delivery of staff of the Anambra state civil service has been a recurring issue, which most of administrators have tried to address with little success. Various administrations have initiated reform measures that were aimed at making the public organization more efficient and result-oriented Mitchell, (2000). The primary function of government organization anywhere in the world is to provide welfare service and protect the lives of the citizen. In this effect, one can safely say that the civil service is part and parcel of the government and governance Onah (2000) though its role is more visible in the area of policy implementation, the bureaucracy is as much involved in policy initiation. 'To be effective and efficient in the 21st century, public sector organization needs to adopt a sound and innovative service delivery tool'. Nkwe, (2012), thus, the digitalization of governance received rapid acceptance worldwide in the 1990s. E-governance, which stands for electronic governance became the new focus of modern day governments which is all about using ICTs to support and enhance the delivery of public goods and services. Finally, the advent and deployment of information communication technology (ICT) in public services presents opportunities for its use to facilitate effective service delivery as many countries have embraced it as a way forward. Poor service delivery of staff is experienced in the form of epileptic services, inadequate responsiveness to the citizens, corruption and general non-service delivery of duty as at when due. This scenario continues to be evident in the Civil Service Commission particularly in developing economies that are yet to embrace the opportunities of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Delay in service delivery, lack of proper records, corruption charges and other unethical conducts associated with manual traditional style of service delivery. Alao and Alao, (2013) consider these as forms of set-back that affect service delivery of staff and create room for ineffectiveness and inefficiency in the civil service. These consequences of poor service delivery of staff of civil service mostly result to improper accountability, lack of transparency, high cost of administration, wastage and lack of commitment in making services work for the citizenry (World Bank, 2012). These problems have led to the implementation of various reforms aimed at improving efficiency and effectiveness. It is in realization of this absolute necessity that this study tries to examine the E-governance and service delivery of staff of Anambra State Civil Service Commission, Awka.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to ascertain the effect of E-governance on service delivery of Anambra State civil service. The specific objectives are:

- 1) To ascertain the effect of technology infrastructure on service delivery in Anambra State civil service.
- 2) To determine the effect of digital service availability on service delivery in Anambra State civil service.
- 3) To ascertain the degree to which e-planning affects service delivery in Anambra State civil service.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE 2.0 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 E-Governance

E-governance can be referred to as the application of information communication technology by the government to enhance accountability, create awareness and ensure transparency in the management of government business. It is a political strategy through which the activities of government are made known through the adoption of modern communication technology (Ojo, 2014). According to Estevez and Janowski (2013), Electronic Governance is the application of technology by government to transform itself and its interactions with customers, in order to create an impact on the society. Fatile (2012), defines E-governance as the use of information technologies (such as the internet, the World Wide Web and mobile computing) by government agencies that can transform their relationship with citizens, business, different areas of government, and other government.

2.1.2 Service Delivery

Service delivery simply means the extent to which an individual, unit or department of an organization discharge their assigned or statutory responsibilities. It is also a means by which an organization evaluates an individual employee or unit input and output level especially in the area of attaining set goals or task assigned. In the view of Byars and Rue (2006), service delivery is the degree to which an employee accomplished the tasks that made his or her job. El-Rufai (2006) summarizes service delivery as the degree of an organization and/or employee performance, output and productivity in the discharge of their responsibilities within the available time, money and other resources, towards the achievement of overall goals, of the organization.

2.2 Empirical Studies

Ogu and Chukwurah, (2023) investigated e-governance and public service delivery in Nigeria: A study of, Anambra State Civil Service: 2018-2022. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Survey research design was adapted for the study. The population of the study comprised 6,955 employees in Anambra State Civil Service, out of which a sample size of 361 staff were draw using Krejcie and Morgan's sample size determination table. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. Data collected were analyzed using frequency, percentages, mean, standard deviation and t-test. The findings of the study revealed among others that Anambra State Civil Service apply e-governance in public service delivery to high extent. It was also found out that the application of e-governance has positively affected public service delivery in Anambra State Civil Service. Obi, Uzor & Chukwurah (2020) determined the extent e-governance implementation has enhanced administrative efficiency in the Nigeria Civil Service and to ascertain whether the implementation of e-governance has helped to reduce corruption in the Nigeria Civil Service. The paper relied on modernization theory and qualitative research method as data that formed major part of the study were generated from secondary sources. Findings reveal that e-governance has made service delivery easier which is evident in the ways and manner the old methods have been transformed and researchers recommend for Nigeria's public service to show high level of e-readiness in their operations on one part and government adequate provision of necessary infrastructure; enact Information and Communication

Technology for successful implementation on the other part. Enwelu and Nnaji, (2023) examined the effect of e-governance on employee service delivery in Anambra State Civil Service Commission, Awka. The study was anchored on technology determinism theory. The study was guided by three research questions and hypotheses. The study adopted the survey design. It relied on primary and secondary data, and simple random sampling techniques were used to select the sample population. The data collected were presented in frequency table and simple percentage. T-test statistical technique was used with the aid of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) to test the research hypotheses. Findings of the study show that e-governance facilities are available for use in Anambra State Civil Service Commission, Awka. It also discovered that the use of electronic governance improve accessibility to government information service delivery in Anambra State Civil Service Commission, Awka. Nnamani, et.al. (2023) examined the extent electronic governance and social service delivery has improved public bureaucracies in Nigeria. Specifically, the study will find out the extent the adoption of electronic governance encourages quality service delivery in implementing the policies and programmes in Nigeria public sector. Communication theory was adopted as its framework; this theory tries to elucidate that communication is one of the ingredients that makes a system effective in contemporary society. Electronic government makes an impact on the knowledge of the society as well as on the literate level of the society. The adoption of e- governance in running the affairs of the ministries brings about effective service delivery in Nigeria. It helps in define and re-define the current vision and mission of the government and curtails the level of corruption, encourages accountability and transparency in governance since it serves as a yardstick for auditing in governance. E-governance in bureaucracies helps to facilitate formulation of strategies for policy implementation in Nigeria. Mahmoud and Aririguzo (2024) examined the patterns of interaction with e-governance and determining its impact on sustainable development in Nigeria are the aims of this study. This study used the content analysis technique and relied on secondary sources for its data. The results of this research demonstrate that Nigeria has not yet made full use of e-governance and the forms of engagement it offers. Findings from this study however indicate that sustainable development in Nigeria can be greatly advanced

through the effective application of several egovernance relationship patterns. Ntadom, Atueyi & Jacobs. (2021) examined the effect of career development on organizational performance, a Study of selected higher institution in Anambra State Nigeria. The study was anchored on Self-concept theory of career development. As a cross-sectional survey the research design were used, a structured questionnaire instrument were developed and used for data collection by the researcher to which reflect such options as strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree, which is popularly referred as five (5)points likert scale. It was used to obtain information from the respondents. The population of the study comprised of 57, 710 students selected across the five south east states of Nigeria. A sample size of 399students was drawn from the population, using Taro Yamane formular of which three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaires were duly completed and returned; showing 96% response rate. Research hypotheses were tested using ANOVA regression analysis which was carried out with the aid of Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. The study found that career development has significant effect on Organizational Performance.

Ezeamama, (2019) investigated the relationship between job satisfaction and employee productivity in Anambra State University. The study was a survey research design based on a sample of 312 staff of the population of then onteaching staff of the Anambra State University. The cross sectional survey was conducted between January, 8 2013 and February 11, 2013. A questionnaire was developed on which the respondents indicated their level of agreement based on five-point Likert scales ranging from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 5 (“strongly agree”). Cronbach’s alpha (α) analysis (0.75 for job satisfaction and 0.84 for productivity) test the internal consistency of the variables obtained in the sample showed that the instrument is reliable. Descriptive statistics: Mean standard, frequencies and percentages were used to analyse the demographic characteristics and answer the research questions, while the Freidman’s Chi-square test was used on hypotheses one and two while Spearman’s ranked correlation analysis was adopted to test the hypotheses three. The SPSS version 17 for windows (a computer based statistical programme) was used to run all the analyses for the study. The results showed that the employees of Anambra State University are significantly satisfied from the job they do and

are significantly productive. Further results indicated that there is very weak positive but insignificant relationship between job satisfaction and employee productivity in Anambra State University. The study thus concluded that job satisfaction is not a contributor to the employee productivity in the public sector of Nigeria, as the Institutions do not cue their plans towards satisfying the needs of the employees Ezeamama Orji, and Obani, (2024). Analyzed the job design and employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The objective of the study was to determine the effect of job description on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Evaluate the effect of skill variety on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra, State, Nigeria. Two research hypotheses were formulated in line with the objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; the sample techniques employed simple random sampling. The population for this research work is 432 respondents. The researcher distributes four hundred and thirty-two (432) questionnaires but only four hundred and nine (409) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Correlation and ttest were used to test the hypothesis. The finding of the study shows that Job description has significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Skill variety has significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra, State, Nigeria. The study recommends vegetable oil firms can create jobs that are challenging, rewarding, and aligned with employee motivations, ultimately leading to increased job satisfaction, productivity, and employee retention Nwanolue, Ezeamama, & Okeke, (2022) examine the issues surrounding oil terrorism and environmental protection in the Niger Delta region.

Specifically, it seeks to find out how oil resource has contributed to environmental-protection challenge in the Niger Delta region, what factors exacerbate oil terrorism and environmentalprotection challenge in the region as well as the practical solutions that can effectively end oilrelated conflicts in the region. The study is anchored on regulatory capture theory while qualitative approach is adopted for data collection and analysis. Among other things, the study found out that environmental degradation persists as a result of weak regulatory approach by government. It equally found out that the oil companies operating in the region have successfully captured the regulators and continued to engage in unending flouting of the

extant environmental-protection laws. In view of the findings, the study recommended the need for strict regulation against compromise of collective interest in the region. It also recommended the setting up of local surveillance team of activists with a responsibility to independently provide quarterly report to government on matters pertaining to the environment. Ezeamama & Obani, (2024) analyzed the role of civic education in curbing electoral malpractice in Nigeria. The objective of the study were To find out whether civic education is a measure of curbing corruption in Nigeria; examine the effect of Education of tolerance on curbing electoral malpractice in Nigeria; examine the effect of human right education on curbing electoral malpractice in Nigeria. Three research hypothesis and three research questions are formulated in line with the above objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; the sample techniques employed simple random sampling. The population for this research work is 257,422, respondents. It comprises of the three Local Government Area (LGA) while the sample size is 399 through Taro Yamane formula. The researcher distributes three hundred and ninety-nine (399) questionnaires but only three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Structured questionnaire were use to gather information from the population. Percentage tables and ANOVA method of data analysis was used to test the questionnaire. The finding of the study shows that Civic education has significant impact on curbing electoral malpractice in Nigeria; Education of tolerance has significant impact on curbing electoral malpractice in Nigeria; Human right education has significant impact on curbing electoral malpractice in Nigeria. Ezeamama & Orji, (2024). Analyzed the gender equality and women participation in politics in Idemili North L.G.A. in Anambra State. The objective of the study is to find out whether gender inequality has affected women participation in politics in Idemili North L.G.A. in Anambra State; examine the level of women participation in politics in Idemili North L.G.A. in Anambra State; examine the effect of woman participation in politics on development of Idemili North L.G.A. in Anambra State. Three research hypothesis and three research questions are formulated in line with the above objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; the sample techniques employed simple random sampling. The population for this research work is 4212, women. It comprises of all the women in Idemili in Anambra state from the age of 30 and above while the sample size is 809 through Borg & Gall (1973) formular. The researcher distributes eight hundred and nine (809) questionnaires but only seven hundred and forty-two (742) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Structured questionnaire were use to gather information from the population. Percentage tables and ANOVA method of data analysis was used to test the questionnaire. The finding of the study shows that Gender inequality has significant influence women participation in politics in Idemili North L.G.A. in Anambra State. There are factors responsible for levels of women participation in politics in Idemili North L.G.A. in Anambra State. Woman participation in politics has significant effect on development of Idemili North L.G.A. in Anambra State. Ezeamama and Ofozoba (2023) analyzed the role of Local Governments in rural development of Nigeria, a case study of Ekwusigo Local Government Area of Anambra State The objective of the study were to Evaluate the contribution of local government to agricultural development in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Examine the role of local government on infrastructural development in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Assess the contributions of local government on employment creation Ekwusigo Local

Government in Anambra State. Three research hypothesis and three research questions are formulated in line with the above objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; the sample techniques employed was simple random sampling. The study selected Ekwusigo Local Government Area, the population are 99242 where the sample size is 398 using Taro Yamane formula. The researcher distributes Three hundred and ninety-eight (398) questionnaires but only three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Structured questionnaire was use to gather information from the population. Percentage tables and ANOVA method of data analysis was used to test the questionnaire. The finding of the study shows that; Local government has made significant contributions to agricultural development in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Local government has contributed to infrastructural development in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State. Local government has made significant contributions to employment creation in Ekwusigo Local Government in Anambra State.

Source: Field Survey, 2025 Table 4.1 showed that a total number of four hundred and eighty-seven (487) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, four hundred and seventy-four (474) copies which represented 97% were returned, four hundred, fifty-nine (459) which represent 94% where completed and thirteen (13) copies which represented 2% were not duly completed by the respondents, while seven (7) copies which represented only 1% of the total questionnaire were missing. Hence, the analyses for this study were based on the four hundred and fifty-nine (459) copies which represented 94% of the sample population.

4.2 TEST OF STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESES

HO₁: Technology infrastructure has no significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra State civil service

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Table 4.2.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.731 ^a	.582	.577	.66768	.282	59.43	3	45	.000	1.688
						7		5		

Predictors: (Constant), EPL, DSA, TEINF

Dependent Variable: SD

Table 4.3.1 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 0.58%. This implies that 58% of the variation in service delivery is explained by variations in technology infrastructure, digital service availability and eplanning. This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.57%. Test for autocorrelation: This is used test whether errors corresponding to different observation are uncorrelated. If the value of the durbin-watson from the regression result is close to 2 no autocorrelation in that regression result, but if it deviates significantly

then there is autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic (D.W) of 2 reveals no autocorrelation in the models. Hence, the result is good for business analysis because the Durbin Watson result is 1.688

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	79.491	3	26.497	59.437	.000 ^b
	Residual	202.840	455	.446		
	Total	282.331	458			

a. Dependent Variable: SD

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	2.433	.290		8.395	.00	1.864	3.003
	TEINF	.334	.027	.504	12.540	.00	.282	.386
	DSA	.092	.046	.080	2.007	.045	.182	.002
	EPL	.169	.033	.207	5.154	.00		.233

a. Dependent Variable: SD

A priori Criteria: This is based on current business theories and provides information on the amount and signs of the business parameter under consideration. Given that technology infrastructure has a positive sign and a value of .334 in the table above, it follows that a rise in technology infrastructure will boost service delivery in civil service in Anambra State by 34%, which is consistent with the a priori expectation. Given that digital service availability has a positive sign and a value of .092, it follows that an increase in digital service availability will result in a 9% increase in service delivery in civil service in Anambra State. Given that E-planning has a positive sign and a value of .169, it follows that an increase

in E-planning will boost service delivery in civil service in Anambra State by 16%, as predicted by theory. T-Statistics: The t-test is used to determine each explanatory parameter's statistical significance in the model. Technology infrastructure has a ttest of 12.543, which is statistically significant and suggests that it has a considerable impact on service delivery in civil service in Anambra State. Digital service availability is 2.007 which is statistically significant this has had a substantial impact on service delivery in civil service in Anambra State at the 5% level of significance. The statistical significance of Eplanning is 5.154, which suggests that it strongly contributes to service delivery in civil service in Anambra State at the 5% level of significance.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses Hypothesis One

HO₁: Technology infrastructure has no significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra State civil service Knowledge retention has a t-statistics of 12.543 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypotheses which state Technology infrastructure has significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra

State civil service

Hypothesis Two

HO₂: Digital service availability has no significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra State civil service in testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. Knowledge storage variables have a t-statistics of 2.007 and a probability value of 0.045 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Digital service availability has significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra State civil service

Hypothesis Three

HO₂: E-Planning has no significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra State civil service E-Planning has a t-statistics of 5.154 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that E-Planning has significant positive effect on service delivery in Anambra State civil service

Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, e-governance has the potential to significantly improve service delivery in the civil service of Anambra State. By leveraging information and communication technologies (ICTs), government agencies can automate processes, enhance transparency, and increase efficiency, resulting in better public services and greater citizen satisfaction. However, successful implementation of e-governance requires strong leadership, a clear strategy, adequate funding, and effective change management. By addressing these challenges and capitalizing on the benefits of e-governance, Anambra State can become a model for modern, efficient, and responsive government. Civil service should develop a comprehensive e-governance strategy that define the goals, objectives, and priorities for e-governance and create a roadmap for implementation. Civil service should Train and empower government employees, Provide training and support to help government

employees adapt to new technologies and processes. Civil service should Invest in technology infrastructure and ensure that government agencies have the necessary hardware, software, and internet connectivity to support e-governance initiatives.

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